

MIGWELL Interview Outlines and Questionnaire

Deliverable 3.1.

MIGWELL

Well-being and Migration:
The Hungary – Austria Migration Nexus

Lilla Tóth, Borbála Göncz, Josef Kohlbacher, György Lengyel,
Ádám Németh, Zsolt Németh, László Zöldi

2023

This working paper was developed in the context of the project **MIGWELL – Well-being and Migration: the Hungary – Austria Migration Nexus**

Work Package 3: ‘Additional surveys’

MIGWELL is an FWF–NKFIH International Joint Project. In Austria the project is funded by the Austrian Science Fund. In Hungary the project has been implemented with the support provided by the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund (Ministry of Innovation and Technology of Hungary), financed under the ANN funding scheme.

Project code: I 5616 (in Austria), 139465 (in Hungary)

Project duration: 01.02.2022 – 31.07.2025 (in Austria), 01.12.2021 – 31.05.2025 (in Hungary)

Project Partners:

Institute for Urban and Regional Research at the Austrian Academy of Sciences
Centre for Empirical Social Research at the Corvinus University of Budapest
Department of Finno-Ugrian Studies, University of Vienna

Scientific Advisory Board:

Department of Sociology, University of Vienna
Hungarian Demographic Research Institute
Hungarian Central Statistical Office

MIGWELL’s website: [LINK](#)

MIGWELL’s outputs will be uploaded to: [LINK](#)

Inquiries can be directed to: Institute for Urban and Regional Research at the Austrian Academy of Sciences, isr@oeaw.ac.at or Centre for Empirical Social Research at the Corvinus University of Budapest, borbala.goncz@uni-corvinus.hu

Suggested citation: Tóth, L., Göncz, B., Kohlbacher, J., Lengyel, Gy., Németh, Á., and Németh, Zs. (2023) *MIGWELL Interview Outlines and Questionnaire*. MIGWELL Deliverable 3.1., 81 p.

Table of contents

1. Narrative interviews	4
1.1 Hungarian migrants in Austria	4
1.2 Potential stayers and potential migrants in Hungary	18
1.3 Hungarian return migrants in Hungary	31
2. Cognitive interviews.....	45
2.1. Discussion of the questionnaire.....	45
2.2. Basic socio-demographic data & “Filter questions”	46
2.3. Spatial data	46
2.4. Migration intention and decision.....	46
2.5. Objective indicators of well-being	46
2.6. Subjective well-being.....	48
2.7. Trust	48
2.8. Final questions: monthly income	48
3. Survey questionnaire	49

MIGWELL at a glance

The MIGWELL project focuses on the nexus of migration and well-being in Hungary and Austria. Using quantitative and qualitative research methods, it seeks to explore the impacts of migration on subjective well-being in the case of Hungarian immigrants in Austria as well as the effects of subjective well-being differences on emigration potential in Hungary. The approach of this project is innovative not only because it links the concepts of ‘well-being’ and ‘migration’, but also because it interprets their two-way causal relationship within one research framework. Since the Covid-19 pandemic might have a profound impact on both pillars, MIGWELL will also reflect on the rapidly changing socio-economic and well-being related issues that have emerged due to the epidemic throughout the life cycle of the project. The theoretical expansion of these concepts and the empirical findings of the project may contribute to more effective policies in both countries.

1. Narrative interviews

1.1 Hungarian migrants in Austria

Introduction:

The aim of our research is to assess how and under what circumstances immigrants from Hungary settled in Austria and came to this decision. We want to find out what differences they perceive between the two countries that determine their decision and what expectations and hopes they have.

This part of the research consists of an interview lasting about an hour and a half, which will be audio-recorded to facilitate the processing of the findings. The audio recording will be treated confidentially, your name will not be used in the analysis of the research and you will not be identified in the study summarising the results. (At this point, get signed the Informed Consent.)

We also have to ask about COVID pandemic impact on almost everything !!!

I - Narrative section

First, I would like you to tell the story how you came to be in Austria.

[First let the respondent talk about the topic on his/her own and highlight the aspects that are important to him/her]

II - Elaboration on what has been said before

[If the respondent did not talk or did not talk in sufficient detail about the issues of interest to us, ask him/her as follows, refer to what already has been mentioned.]

E.g. You mentioned that you lost your job, can you please tell me more about this.

1. The reasons for migration

I would like you to tell me a little more about what reasons and considerations you had as you came to Austria.

[The plural helps to remain complex.]

Can you tell us how you arrived here? Let's clarify what you have said and ask for details.

[What we want to know:

- active/passive
- whether you wanted to come here
- did you want to stay here
- reason, what motivated him/her: what were the push and pull effects (what attracted him/her, what repelled him/her), (all dimensions relevant to the interviewee)

- aspirations and capabilities
- circumstances
- when and where he came from
- what difficulties did you encounter
- were there and what were the intermediate stops between Hungary and Austria, e.g. commuting in Austria
- From what sources, what information have you gathered?
- Did you have any relatives, friends or acquaintances you could rely on to help you carry out your plan?
- Did you have any relatives, friends or acquaintances in Austria that you could rely on after your arrival?
- Did you come to Austria alone or with others?
- Have you previously spent a longer period (3 months? 1 year?) abroad outside Austria?
- Before moving to Austria, did you have other countries in mind as possible destinations? Which country(ies)? Why did you finally choose Austria?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your emigration plans?]

2 Establishment of the legal framework for residence in Austria, start of residence in Austria

We have not yet discussed how you obtained the necessary documents for your stay in Austria. Can you tell us how this was done?

[What we want to know:

- Contact with institutions, positive, negative, typical experiences
- administration]

Did you receive any help from individuals or from any institutions, foundations, churches, NGOs at the beginning of your stay? Can you tell us about this?

[- Did you come into contact with Hungarians here, how, did you receive help from them? Please specify, what contacts you had (same residence, workplace etc)?

- do you remember how your first evening here was
- how you started to organize your life in Austria
- how you got your first flat and housing]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your resettlement-related administration?

3 Family, friends, partner before and after migration -

The topic of family, friends and partner has already been discussed. Could you tell us more about your personal relationships? Personally who are the most important people for you?

Were there people whom you had to leave behind? Do you have new friends/partners etc. here? How did they influence your migration plan?

[What we want to know:

- social connections that he/or she perceives most important in terms of degree of their influence on migration and SWB
- before and especially after migration - what relationships were maintained and what new ones were formed
- did you receive and what help on arrival from your personal network, from whom?]
- Are you in a couple relationship? If not, have you previously lived in a couple relationship in Austria? Your partner is: a) Hungarian; b) another immigrant - what nationality?; c) Austrian.
- Are there any children born of your couple relationship, do you have children together? What language do they speak at home?
- Did you move from Hungary with your partner?
- Do you regularly / occasionally send financial support to relatives living in Hungary?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your personal relations? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your personal relations?]

4 Work

Tell me about your situation in Hungary before the time of departure to Austria. What kind of jobs did you and your family members have? How did you make your living in Hungary? What was your life in Hungary? Who (from the family) has left before or tried before you?

I would like you to tell me a little more about how you found work in Austria. What different activities does your family do for a living?

[What we want to know:

- what kind of jobs you have had; what was your first job; what were the characteristics of your first job compared to your job at home
- what is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are your bosses and subordinates
- are you satisfied with your job
- is his/her education appropriate
- legal, declared versus black or grey employment
- how different is his situation in this area from that of an average Austrian citizen]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your labour market position plans?

5 Relationship with the host society

I would like you to tell me a little bit more about how you see the people here, how you feel in Austria.

What do you know about the other immigrant groups (Turks, Syrians, Romanians, Afghans, Bosnians, Poles, Serbs, etc.)? How do you compare your situation with theirs in terms of living, acceptance and support?

[What we want to know:

- Integration (work, education, rights, language: do you learn German, do you think it is important, what languages do your children speak, why)
- attitude of the host society,
- defining experiences from this point of view: what was the worst, what was the best thing that happened to her in Austria,
- how his own individual situation differs from that of Hungarians in Austria in general,
- how the authorities, the social environment treat him (respectfully, correctly), whether he gets what is due to him,
- compared to the situation in Hungary, is it better or worse in this respect
- good/bad experiences]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your relation with the host society?]

6 Objective well-being/non-material resources – Health, Work-life balance, Education and skills, Civic engagement

Health

- *Tell me about your health status! Do you have any health problem?*
- How would you measure your situation regarding your health? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your health status?

Work-life balance

How is your life regarding work and leisure activities? Do you have enough time you can spend doing the things you like?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your time spending with leisure activities? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your work-life balance?

Education and skills

What are your educational and professional qualifications? What important work experience do you have? How do your qualifications fit with your jobs?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your qualifications and experience? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your factual work experiences, skills and your professional ambitions ?

Civic engagement

„The key indicators of civic engagement and governance presented here refer to voter turnout and the existence of formal and open consultation processes on rule making.

... Voter participation is a proxy for civic and political engagement and of how this can effectively shape the society where people live. Information on electoral participation should be complemented by measures of other types of participation in society and institutional trust. The indicator of open consultation processes refers to the existence of institutional practices, but does neither gauge whether these procedures are effective nor whether they are used by citizens. Comparability of this index can also be limited by cultural, institutional and historical contexts. Ideally indicators of the quality of governance should measure whether public policy is effective and transparent in achieving its goals. Broader measures of civic engagement and governance, sometimes based on specific survey modules, are available for only a few OECD countries.”¹

There are two options

a) use an open question:

Other than voting in political elections, in what other ways are you actively involved in society?

[What we want to know:

- How would you measure your situation regarding your level of activity in public affairs? Is it higher or lower than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- Have done or haven't done any of the followings:

contacted a politician or civil servant, attended political meeting or a rally of a political party; participated in the work of a political organization or movement; worn or displayed a campaign badge or sticker; signed a petition; taken part in a public demonstration; boycotted certain products; bought certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons; donated money to a political organization; participated in illegal protest activities; contacted or appeared in the press to express his views; phoned into a radio programme; did voluntary work for an NGO or civil organization;

- How was it in HUNGARY?

¹ The Compendium of OECD Well-being Indicators' (OECD, 2011b)

- What do you expect this to change in the future?]

OR

b) follow the guide below

- *Have you done or haven't done any of the followings:*

- contacted a politician or civil servant,
- attended political meeting or a rally of a political party;
- participated in the work of a political organization or movement;
- worn or displayed a campaign badge or sticker;
- signed a petition;
- taken part in a public demonstration;
- boycotted certain products;
- bought certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons;
- donated money to a political organization;
- participated in illegal protest activities;
- contacted or appeared in the press to express his views;
- phoned into a radio programme;
- did voluntary work for an NGO or civil organization;
- voted in national and local elections.

- *Would you say that most people can be trusted?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in others? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the political system?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the political system? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the in the legal system?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the legal system? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the in the police?*
- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the police? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the press, tv, radio*
- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the press, tv, radio? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

7 Social connections

Micro level

Do you have anyone to discuss personal matters with?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to discuss your personal matters with someone? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Do you have any relatives, friends or neighbours that you can ask for help?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to ask for help from relatives, friends or neighbours? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Mezo level

Are you connected to the people who live here? To what extent?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to be connected to people living here? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Macro level

How do you feel about the Austrian state bureaucracy? What are your personal experiences and impressions?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your experiences and impressions about the Austrian state bureaucracy? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

8 Environmental quality/ Safety and security

Overall, how satisfied are you with the quality of your present living environment?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the quality of your present environment? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your feelings about environmental quality?

How safe do you feel walking alone in your present area after dark?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the safety of your current area? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

9 Subjective well-being

9.1 Affect and 9.2 Eudaimonic well-being

There are two options

a) to use an open question:

How do you feel psychologically nowadays? What are your feelings, moods and states of mind?

OR

b) follow the detailed guide below:

How much of the time over the past four weeks

(All of the time, Most of the time; Some of the time, A little of the time; None of the time; 1-5)

Have you been very nervous?

Have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?

Have you felt calm and peaceful?

Have you felt downhearted and depressed?

Have you been happy?

[What we want to know:

- How would you measure your situation regarding your moods and feelings? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?]

- How has the Covid outbreak affected your overall mental state?

9.2 Eudaimonic well-being

Overall, to what extent do you feel that the things you do in your life are worthwhile?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the feeling that what you do is worthwhile? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

How desperate or optimistic are you about the future?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the level of your optimism? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

9.3 Domain satisfaction –

the way of conducting the interview from now on depends on the time available and the other circumstances of the interview

There are two options:

a) to use an open question, as follows:

What are the things you need to feel satisfied with your life? Please list!

What is not so important or not important at all?

Have you always felt this way or has it changed? When, why?

[What we want to know:

the relative importance of the domain satisfaction mindsets,

how they change over time,

their relationship with life events, and

satisfaction with each domain, and

the reference group to which the respondents compare and measure themselves]

OR

b) follow the detailed instructions below

Please rate the following items according to their necessity for your personal well-being. Use a three-point scale (0 to 2, where 0 represents 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary').

The financial situation of your household - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the financial situation of your household? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your accommodation - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your accommodation? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your present work - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your present work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Commuting time - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the time you commute to work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

The amount of time you have to do things you like doing - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the amount of time you have to do things you like? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your personal relationships - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your personal relationships? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

The quality of your living environment – 0 ‘unnecessary’, 1 ‘necessary’ and 2 ‘very necessary’

- How would you measure your situation regarding the quality of your living environment? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with that?
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

[What we want to know

What are the things and conditions which are important that make him feel satisfied?

In what dimensions does she define satisfaction?

To whom, to whom/to what groups does he measure his situation when it comes to describing his satisfaction with his life?

Has this changed in his/her life? How?

- The things that are important that determine his satisfaction?
- The people or social groups against which he measures or has measured his situation? In Hungary and Austria? In the past and now?]

10 Objective well-being/material resources - Income and living conditions

Tell us about your living conditions!

Work

- What is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are - your bosses and subordinates? What are your working conditions like?
- Does your current job match your professional qualifications?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Housing

- Tell us about your accommodation you live in!

- How big is the apartment, how many people live in it, how is it equipped, and what is the neighborhood like?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your accommodation? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your living conditions?

Income

- How much is your monthly income now (in Euro, for you / the family you live with) - how do you measure this (previous income in Hungary / Austrian colleagues, Austrians, immigrants, professional group, etc.)
- How would you measure your situation regarding your income? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What was it like in HUNGARY (in forint)?
- What do you expect, how will it change in the future?

Wealth

- What notable assets do you have (apartment, holiday home, car, share in a business)?
- Do you have savings?
- How secure you feel concerning the next two years financially?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your wealth? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

11 Overall life satisfaction

Overall, how satisfied are you with your life these days?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the safety of your current area? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your overall life satisfaction?

12 Vision for the future

What do you think your personal future will be like, how will your career develop?

[What we want to know:

- What do they want, what do they aspire to and what is realistic, what is most likely to happen to them?
- Where, what will his/her status be in 5-10 years, what will his/her citizenship be?
- Where and how do you envision your children's future? What social position will they achieve, where geographically, what kind of companion do they want to have by their side?]

1.2 Potential stayers and potential migrants in Hungary

Introduction:

The aim of our research is to assess how and under what circumstances immigrants from Hungary settled in Austria and came to this decision. We want to find out what differences they perceive between the two countries that determine their decision and what expectations and hopes they have.

This part of the research consists of an interview lasting about an hour and a half, which will be audio-recorded to facilitate the processing of the findings. The audio recording will be treated confidentially, your name will not be used in the analysis of the research and you will not be identified in the study summarising the results. (At this point, get signed the Informed Consent.)

We also have to ask about COVID pandemic impact on almost everything !!!

I - Narrative section

First, I would like you to tell the story how you came to the decision to go to Austria.

[First let the respondent talk about the topic on his/her own and highlight the aspects that are important to him/her]

II - Elaboration on what has been said before

[If the respondent did not talk or did not talk in sufficient detail about the issues of interest to us, ask him/her as follows, refer to what already has been mentioned.]

E.g. You mentioned that you lost your job, can you please tell me more about this.

1. The reasons for migration

I would like you to tell me a little more about what reasons and considerations you had as you came to the decision to go to Austria.

[The plural helps to remain complex.]

Let's clarify what you have said and ask for details.

[What we want to know:

- active/passive
- whether you wanted to come there
- do you want to stay there
- reason, what motivated him/her: what were the push and pull effects (what attracted him/her, what repelled him/her), (all dimensions relevant to the interviewee)
- aspirations and capabilities
- circumstances

- when and where he plans to go
- what difficulties did he encounter so far
- were there and what were the intermediate stops between Hungary and Austria, e.g. commuting in Austria
- From what sources, what information have you gathered?
- Did you have any relatives, friends or acquaintances you could rely on to help you carry out your plan?
- Did you have any relatives, friends or acquaintances in Austria that you could rely on after your arrival?
- Do you go to Austria alone or with others?
- Have you previously spent a longer period (3 months? 1 year?) abroad outside Austria?
- Before moving to Austria, did you have other countries in mind as possible destinations? Which country(ies)? Why did you finally choose Austria?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your emigration plans?]

2 Establishment of the legal framework for residence in Austria, start of residence in Austria

We have not yet discussed how you plan to obtain the necessary documents for your stay in Austria. Can you tell us how this is going to be?

[What we want to know:

- Contact with institutions, positive, negative, typical experiences
- administration]

Did you receive any help from individuals or from any institutions, foundations, churches, NGOs at that period of your preparation for stay? Can you tell us about this?

[- Did you come into contact with Hungarians there, how, did you receive help from them? Please specify, what contacts you had (same residence, workplace etc)?

- how would you start to organize your life in Austria
- how would you get your first flat and housing]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your resettlement-related plan?

3 Family, friends, partner before and after migration -

The topic of family, friends and partner has already been discussed. Could you tell us more about your personal relationships? Personally who are the most important people for you? Are there people whom you have to leave behind? Do you have new friends/partners etc. there? How did they influence your migration plan?

[What we want to know:

- social connections that he/or she perceives most important in terms of degree of their influence on migration and SWB

- before and especially after migration - what relationships were maintained and what new ones were formed
- will you receive and what help on arrival from your personal network, from whom?]
- Are you in a couple relationship? Your partner is: a) Hungarian; b) another immigrant - what nationality?; c) Austrian.
- Are there any children born of your couple relationship, do you have children together? What language do they speak at home?
- Do you move from Hungary with your partner?
- Do you plan to (regularly / occasionally) send financial support to relatives living in Hungary?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your personal relations? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your personal relations?]

4 Work

Tell me about your situation in Hungary before the time of departure to Austria. What kind of jobs do you and your family members have? How do you make your living in Hungary? What is your life in Hungary? Who (from the family) has left before or tried before you?

I would like you to tell me a little more about how you plan to find job in Austria. What different activities does your family do for a living?

[What we want to know:

- what kind of jobs you have had; what is your first job going to be; what are the characteristics of your first future job compared to your present job at home
- what is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are your bosses and subordinates
- are you satisfied with your job
- is your education appropriate
- legal, declared versus black or grey employment
- how different is your situation in this area from that of an average Hungarian/Austrian citizen]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your labour market position plans?

5 Relationship with the host society

I would like you to tell me a little bit more about how you see the people here, how you feel in Hungary? How do you think about Austria in this respect?

What do you know about the other social groups and migrants in Austria (Turks, Syrians, Romanians, Afghans, Bosnians, Poles, Serbs, etc.)? How do you compare your situation with theirs in terms of living, acceptance and support?

[What we want to know:

- Integration (work, education, rights, language: do you learn German, do you think it is important , what languages do your children speak, why)
- perceived attitude of the host society,
- defining experiences from this point of view: what was the worst, what is the best thing that could happen to him/her in Austria,
- how his own individual situation differs from that of Hungarians in Austria in general,
- how the authorities, the social environment treat him (respectfully, correctly), whether he gets what is due to him,
- compared to the situation in Hungary, is it better or worse in this respect
- good/bad experiences]
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your relation with the host society?]

6 Objective well-being/non-material resources – Health, Work-life balance, Education and skills, Civic engagement

Health

- *Tell me about your health status! Do you have any health problem?*
- How would you measure your situation regarding your health? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your health status?

Work-life balance

How is your life regarding work and leisure activities? Do you have enough time you can spend doing the things you like?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your time spending with leisure activities? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your work-life balance?

Education and skills

What are your educational and professional qualifications? What important work experience do you have? How do your qualifications fit with your jobs?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your qualifications and experience? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your factual work experiences, skills and your professional ambitions ?

Civic engagement

„The key indicators of civic engagement and governance presented here refer to voter turnout and the existence of formal and open consultation processes on rule making.

... Voter participation is a proxy for civic and political engagement and of how this can effectively shape the society where people live. Information on electoral participation should be complemented by measures of other types of participation in society and institutional trust. The indicator of open consultation processes refers to the existence of institutional practices, but does neither gauge whether these procedures are effective nor whether they are used by citizens. Comparability of this index can also be limited by cultural, institutional and historical contexts. Ideally indicators of the quality of governance should measure whether public policy is effective and transparent in achieving its goals. Broader measures of civic engagement and governance, sometimes based on specific survey modules, are available for only a few OECD countries.”²

There are two options

a) use an open question:

Other than voting in political elections, in what other ways are you actively involved in society?

[What we want to know:

- How would you measure your situation regarding your level of activity in public affairs? Is it higher or lower than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- Have done or haven't done any of the followings:

contacted a politician or civil servant, attended political meeting or a rally of a political party; participated in the work of a political organization or movement; worn or displayed a campaign badge or sticker; signed a petition; taken part in a public demonstration; boycotted certain products; bought certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons; donated money to a political organization; participated in illegal protest activities; contacted or appeared in the press to express his views; phoned into a radio programme; did voluntary work for an NGO or civil organization;

- What do you expect this to change in the future?]

OR

b) follow the guide below

- *Have you done or haven't done any of the followings:*

contacted a politician or civil servant,
attended political meeting or a rally of a political party;

² The Compendium of OECD Well-being Indicators' (OECD, 2011b)

participated in the work of a political organization or movement;
 worn or displayed a campaign badge or sticker;
 signed a petition;
 taken part in a public demonstration;
 boycotted certain products;
 bought certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons;
 donated money to a political organization;
 participated in illegal protest activities;
 contacted or appeared in the press to express his views;
 phoned into a radio programme;
 did voluntary work for an NGO or civil organization;
 voted in national and local elections.

- *Would you say that most people can be trusted?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in others? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the political system?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the political system? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the in the legal system?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the legal system? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

- *How much do you personally trust in the in the police?*

- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the police? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- *How much do you personally trust in the press, tv, radio*
- How would you measure your situation regarding your trust in the press, tv, radio? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

7 Social connections

Micro level

Do you have anyone to discuss personal matters with?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to discuss your personal matters with someone? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Do you have any relatives, friends or neighbours that you can ask for help?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to ask for help from relatives, friends or neighbours? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Mezo level

Are you connected to the people who live here? To what extent?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your opportunity to be connected to people living here? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Macro level

How do you feel about the Austrian state bureaucracy? What are your personal experiences and impressions?

- How would you measure your situation regarding your experiences and impressions about the Austrian state bureaucracy? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

8 Environmental quality/ Safety and security

Overall, how satisfied are you with the quality of your present living environment?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the quality of your present environment? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your feelings about environmental quality?

How safe do you feel walking alone in your present area after dark?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the safety of your current area? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

9 Subjective well-being

9.1 Affect and 9.2 Eudaimonic well-being

There are two options

a) to use an open question:

How do you feel psychologically nowadays? What are your feelings, moods and states of mind?

OR

b) follow the detailed guide below:

How much of the time over the past four weeks

(All of the time, Most of the time; Some of the time, A little of the time; None of the time; 1-5)

Have you been very nervous?

Have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?

Have you felt calm and peaceful?

Have you felt downhearted and depressed?

Have you been happy?

[What we want to know:

- How would you measure your situation regarding your moods and feelings? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?]

- How has the Covid outbreak affected your overall mental state?

9.2 Eudaimonic well-being

Overall, to what extent do you feel that the things you do in your life are worthwhile?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the feeling that what you do is worthwhile? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

How desperate or optimistic are you about the future?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the level of your optimism? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

9.3 Domain satisfaction –

the way of conducting the interview from now on depends on the time available and the other circumstances of the interview

There are two options:

a) to use an open question, as follows:

What are the things you need to feel satisfied with your life? Please list!

What is not so important or not important at all?

Have you always felt this way or has it changed? When, why?

[What we want to know:

the relative importance of the domain satisfaction mindsets,

how they change over time,

their relationship with life events, and

satisfaction with each domain, and

the reference group to which the respondents compare and measure themselves]

OR

b) follow the detailed instructions below

Please rate the following items according to their necessity for your personal well-being. Use a three-point scale (0 to 2, where 0 represents 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary').

The financial situation of your household - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the financial situation of your household? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your accommodation - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your accommodation? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your present work - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your present work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Commuting time - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the time you commute to work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with that?

- How was it in HUNGARY?

- What do you expect this to change in the future?

The amount of time you have to do things you like doing - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the amount of time you have to do things you like? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with that?
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Your personal relationships - 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding your personal relationships? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with that?
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

The quality of your living environment – 0 'unnecessary', 1 'necessary' and 2 'very necessary'

- How would you measure your situation regarding the quality of your living environment? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with that?
- How was it in HUNGARY?
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

[What we want to know

What are the things and conditions which are important that make him feel satisfied?

In what dimensions does she define satisfaction?

To whom, to whom/to what groups does he measure his situation when it comes to describing his satisfaction with his life?

Has this changed in his/her life? How?

- The things that are important that determine his satisfaction?
- The people or social groups against which he measures or has measured his situation? In Hungary and Austria? In the past and now?]

10 Objective well-being/material resources - Income and living conditions

Tell us about your living conditions!

Work

- What is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are - your bosses and subordinates? What are your working conditions like?
- Does your current job match your professional qualifications?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your work? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

Housing

- Tell us about your accommodation you live in!
- How big is the apartment, how many people live in it, how is it equipped, and what is the neighborhood like?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your accommodation? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your living conditions?

Income

- How much is your monthly income now (in HUF, for you / the family you live with) - how do you measure this (previous income in Hungary / Austrian colleagues, Austrians, immigrants, professional group, etc.)
- How would you measure your situation regarding your income? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect, how will it change in the future?

Wealth

- What notable assets do you have (apartment, holiday home, car, share in a business)?
- Do you have savings?
- How secure you feel concerning the next two years financially?
- How would you measure your situation regarding your wealth? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?

11 Overall life satisfaction

Overall, how satisfied are you with your life these days?

- How would you measure your situation regarding the safety of your current area? Is it better or worse than? (compared to a reference group chosen by the respondent).
- What do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid outbreak affected your overall life satisfaction?

12 Vision for the future

What do you think your personal future will be like, how will your career develop?

[What we want to know:

- What do they want, what do they aspire to and what is realistic, what is most likely to happen to them?
- Where, what will his/her status be in 5-10 years, what will his/her citizenship be?
- Where and how do you envision your children's future? What social position will they achieve, where geographically, what kind of companion do they want to have by their side?]

1.3 Hungarian return migrants in Hungary

Interview guide

Introduction:

The aim of the research is to assess how and under what circumstances migrants from Hungary to Austria planned to settle in Austria and how they came to this decision, and to explore the circumstances of the decision to return to Hungary.

We would like to find out what differences the returnees perceive between the two countries that determined their decision and what their expectations and hopes were/are in relation to their decision.

This part of the research will consist of an interview lasting about one and a half hours, which will be audio-recorded to facilitate the processing of the results. The audio recording will be treated confidentially, your name will not be used in the analysis of the research, and you will not be identified in the study summarising the results.

We also need to ask about the impact of the COVID pandemic on almost everything!

I - Narrative part

First, I would like you to tell me how you came to the decision to go to Austria. And then to move back to Hungary.

[First let the respondent talk about the topic himself and highlight the aspects that are important to him].

II - Explain what has been said above

[If the respondent did not talk or did not talk in enough detail about the issues of interest to us, ask him/her as follows, referring to the issues already mentioned].

E.g. you mentioned that you lost your job, could you elaborate on this.

1. Reasons for emigration or return migration

I would like you to explain a little more about the reasons and considerations that led you to decide to move to Austria and then why you decided to return to Hungary.

[The plural form helps to keep the question complex.]

Clarify what the interviewee has said and ask for details.

[What we want to know:

- Active/passive
- Did he want to go there
- Did he want to stay there?
- reason, what motivated him/her: what were the repulsive and attractive influences (what attracted him/her, what repelled him/her), (all dimensions relevant to the interviewee).
- ambitions and skills

- circumstances
- when and where they plan to go
- what difficulties he has encountered so far
- whether and what were the intermediate stops between Hungary and Austria, e.g. commuting to Austria
- What sources and information have you gathered? It is very important to mention the role of SOCIAL MEDIA! E.g. Face book groups, prayer groups, unknown people on the internet.
- Did you have any relatives, friends, acquaintances you could rely on to help you implement your plan?
- Do you have any relatives, friends or acquaintances in Australia that you could rely on once you arrive?
- Were you travelling to Austria alone or with others?
- Have you previously spent a longer period of time (3 months? 1 year?) abroad outside Austria?
- Before moving to Austria, did you consider other countries as possible destinations? Which country(ies)? Why did you finally choose Austria?
- How did the Covid epidemic affect your emigration plans?]

2 Establishment of the legal framework for residence in Austria, commencement of residence in Austria/framework for return

We have not yet discussed how you plan to obtain the documents necessary for your stay in Austria. Can you tell us how this will be done?

[What we want to know:

- Contact with institutions, positive, negative, typical experiences.
- administrative procedures]

Have you received any help from individuals or from any institution, foundation, church, NGO during this period of preparation for your stay? Can you tell us about this?

[- Did you have contact with Hungarians there, how, did you receive help from them? Please give details of the contacts you had (same place of residence, workplace, etc.)?

- How did you start organising your life in Austria?
- How did you get your first apartment and housing]
- How did the Covid epidemic affect your plans for resettlement and or return?

3 Family, friends, partner before and after migration/ in Austria and afterwards

Family, friends and partner have already been discussed. Can you tell us more about your personal relationships? Who are the most important people for you personally? Are there people you have left behind either in Hungary or in Austria? Do you have friends/partners etc. there in Austria? How have these influenced your emigration and return plans?

[What we want to know:

- The social contacts you consider most important according to the extent of their impact on migration and SWB.
- Before and especially after migration - what relationships were maintained and what new ones were formed.
- whether and what kind of help he/she received on arrival from his/her personal network, from whom]?
- Are you in a relationship? Partner: a) Hungarian; b) other immigrant - what nationality; c) Austrian.
- Did you have any children from your relationship, do you have children together? What language do they speak at home?
- Have you moved in with your partner?
- Has he/she sent (regular/occasional) financial support to relatives living in Hungary?
- How would you rate your situation in terms of your personal relationships? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your personal relationships].

4 Work - before resettlement/ in Austria /after resettlement in Hungary

Tell us about your situation in Hungary before you left for Austria. What kind of work do you and your family members do? How do you live in Hungary? What is your life like in Hungary? Who (in your family) left before you or tried to leave before you?

I would like you to tell me a bit more about how you plan to find work in Austria. What different activities does your family do for a living?

[What we want to know:

- What kind of job you have had so far; what will be your first job; what are the characteristics of your first future job compared to your current job at home.
- what is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are your bosses and subordinates.
- whether you are satisfied with your job
- is your education appropriate
- whether employment is legal, registered or black or grey
- how different is your situation in this respect from that of an average Hungarian/Austrian citizen].
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your plans for your position in the labour market?

5 Relationship with the host society - - before resettlement/ in Austria /after resettlement in Hungary

I would like you to tell me a little more about how you see the people in Hungary, how you feel in Hungary? What do you think of Austria in this respect, what are the people like there?

What do you know about the other social groups in Hungary and migrants in Austria (Turks, Syrians, Romanians, Afghans, Bosniaks, Poles, Serbs, etc.)? How does your situation compare with theirs in terms of living conditions, acceptance and support?

[What we want to know:

- (work, education, rights, language: do you learn German, do you consider it important, what languages do your children speak, why).
- perceived attitudes of the host society,
- identifying experiences from this point of view: what is the worst, what is the best thing that can happen to them in Austria
- how your own individual situation differs from that of Hungarians in Austria in general,
- how they are treated by the authorities, by the social environment (respectfully, correctly), whether they get what they deserve,
- compared to the situation in Hungary, is it better or worse in this respect.
- good/bad experiences]
- How does/can the Covid epidemic affect your relationship with the host society]?

6 Objective well-being/non-material resources - Health, work-life balance, education and skills, citizenship

- before resettlement/ in Austria /after resettlement in Hungary

Health

- Tell us about your health! Do you have any health problems?
- How would you rate your health? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your health?

Work-life balance

How is your life in terms of work and leisure activities? Do you have enough time to spend doing what you love?

- How do you assess your situation in terms of time spent on leisure activities? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your work-life balance?

Education and skills

What educational and professional qualifications do you have? What relevant work experience do you have? How does your education fit in with your job?

- How would you rate your position in terms of your qualifications and experience? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your actual work experience, skills and professional ambitions?

Citizenship

There are two options

a) use an open question:

Other than voting in political elections, in what other ways are you actively involved in society?

[What we want to know:

- How would you rate your own situation in terms of your level of activity in public affairs? Higher or lower than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

- Did you or did you not do any of the following:

contacted a politician or public official; attended a political rally or a political party meeting; participated in the work of a political organization or movement; wore or displayed a campaign badge or sticker; signed a petition; participated in a public demonstration; boycotted certain products; purchased certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons; donated money to a political organisation; participated in illegal protest actions; contacted or appeared in the press to express an opinion; phoned a radio programme; volunteered for a civil society organisation or NGO;

- How do you think this will change in the future?]

OR

b) follow the guide below

- Did or did not do any of the following:

contacted a politician or public official,

attended a political meeting or a meeting of a political party;

participated in the work of a political organisation or movement;

wore or displayed a campaign badge or sticker;

signed a petition;

participated in a public demonstration;

boycotted certain products;

purchased certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons;

donated money to a political organisation;

participated in illegal protests;

contacted the press or appeared in the press to express his or her views;

phoned into a radio programme;
volunteered for a non-governmental or non-governmental organisation;
voted in national or local elections.

- Do you think most people can be trusted?
- How would you assess your situation in terms of trust in others? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much do you personally trust the political system?
- How would you assess your situation in terms of trust in the political system? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much confidence do you personally have in the legal system?
- How would you rate your situation regarding your confidence in the legal system? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much confidence do you personally have in the police?
- How would you rate your situation regarding your trust in the police? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much do you personally trust the press, television, radio and television?
- How would you assess your situation regarding your trust in the press, TV and radio? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Citizens' engagement

There are two options

a) use an open question:

Other than voting in political elections, in what other ways are you actively involved in society?

[What we want to know:

- How would you rate your own situation in terms of your level of activity in public affairs? Higher or lower than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- Did you or did you not do any of the following:

contacted a politician or public official; attended a political rally or a political party meeting; participated in the work of a political organization or movement; wore or displayed a campaign badge or sticker; signed a petition; participated in a public demonstration; boycotted certain products; purchased certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons; donated money to a political organisation; participated in illegal protest actions; contacted or appeared in the press to express an opinion; phoned a radio programme; volunteered for a civil society organisation or NGO;

- How do you think this will change in the future?]

OR

b) follow the guide below

- Did or did not do any of the following:

contacted a politician or public official,
 attended a political meeting or a meeting of a political party;
 participated in the work of a political organisation or movement;
 wore or displayed a campaign badge or sticker;
 signed a petition;
 participated in a public demonstration;
 boycotted certain products;
 purchased certain products for political, ethical or environmental reasons;
 donated money to a political organisation;
 participated in illegal protests;
 contacted the press or appeared in the press to express his or her views;
 phoned into a radio programme;
 volunteered for a non-governmental or non-governmental organisation;
 voted in national or local elections.

- Do you think most people can be trusted?

- How would you assess your situation in terms of trust in others? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much do you personally trust the political system?

- How would you assess your situation in terms of trust in the political system? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much confidence do you personally have in the legal system?
- How would you rate your situation regarding your confidence in the legal system? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much confidence do you personally have in the police?
- How would you rate your situation regarding your trust in the police? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

- How much do you personally trust the press, television, radio and television?
- How would you assess your situation regarding your trust in the press, TV and radio? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

7 Social relations

- before resettlement/ in Austria /after return to Hungary

Micro level

Is there someone you can discuss your personal matters with?

- How would you rate your situation in terms of having someone to discuss your personal matters with? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Do you have relatives, friends or neighbours you can ask for help?

- How would you rate your situation in terms of having the possibility to ask for help from relatives, friends or neighbours? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Mezo level

Do you have contact with the people who live here? To what extent?

- How would you rate your situation in terms of your ability to connect with people living here? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Macro level

What do you think about the Hungarian state bureaucracy? What are your personal experiences and impressions?

- How would you rate your situation in terms of your experiences and impressions of the Hungarian state bureaucracy? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

8 Quality of the environment/ Safety and security

- before resettlement/ in Austria /after resettlement in Hungary

Overall, how satisfied are you with the quality of your current living environment?

- How would you rate your situation regarding the quality of your current environment? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
 - How do you expect this to change in the future?
 - How has the Covid outbreak affected your feelings about the quality of your environment?
- How safe do you feel walking alone after dark in your current environment?
- How would you rate your situation regarding the safety of your current living environment? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
 - How do you expect this to change in the future?

9 Subjective well-being

9.1 Affective and 9.2 Eudaimonic well-being

There are two options

a) use an open question:

How do you feel emotionally these days? What are/have been your feelings, moods and states of mind?

- in Austria before/after resettlement in Hungary

OR

b) follow the detailed instructions below:

How much time in the last four weeks have you been ...

(All the time, Most of the time; Some of the time, Few of the time; None of the time; 1-5)

Have you been very nervous?

Has he been so moody that nothing could cheer him up?

Did you feel calm and peaceful?

Did he feel depressed and low?

Were you happy?

[What we want to know:

- How do you assess your situation in terms of your mood and feelings? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?].
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your overall mental state?

9.2. Eudaimonic welfare

Overall, to what extent do you feel that the things you do in your life are meaningful?

- How would you measure your position in terms of feeling that what you do makes sense? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

How despaired or optimistic are you about the future?

- How do you assess your situation in terms of your level of optimism? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

9.3 Satisfaction with areas -

the way the interview is conducted will depend on the time available and other circumstances of the interview

There are two options:

(a) use an open question, as follows:

What do you need to feel satisfied with your life? Please list!

What is not so important or not important at all?

Have you always felt this way or has this changed? When, why?

[What we want to know:

Relative importance of satisfaction with each area,

how they change over time,

their relationship to life events, and

satisfaction with other areas, and

the reference group against which respondents compare and measure themselves].

OR

b) follow the detailed instructions below

Please rate the following items according to how necessary they are for your personal well-being. Use a three-point scale (0 to 2, where 0 is "unnecessary", 1 is "necessary" and 2 is "very necessary").

The financial situation of your household -

0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".

- How would you rate the financial situation of your household? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with this?

- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Your place of residence

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".

- How would you rate your housing situation? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How satisfied are you with it?

- What do you expect from future changes?

Your current job

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".

- How would you rate your current job situation? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with it?

- How do you expect it to change in the future?

Commuting time

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".

- How would you rate your situation regarding commuting time to work? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

-How satisfied are you with this?

- How do you expect this to change in the future?

How much time do you have to do the things you like to do

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".

- How would you rate your situation in terms of how much time you have to do things you like? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).

- How satisfied are you with this?

- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Your personal contacts

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".
- How would you rate your situation with regard to your personal contacts? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with this?
- How do you expect it to change in the future?

Quality of your living environment

- 0 "unnecessary", 1 "necessary" and 2 "very necessary".
- How would you rate your situation regarding the quality of your living environment? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How satisfied are you with this?
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

[What we want to know

What are the important things and conditions that make you feel satisfied?

What dimensions do you define satisfaction in?

To whom, to whom/to what groups do you measure your situation when it comes to describing your satisfaction with your life?

Has this changed in your life? How?

- What are the important things that determine your satisfaction?
- The people or social groups to whom you measure or have measured your situation? In Hungary and Austria? In the past and now?]

10 Objective well-being/material resources - Income and living conditions

Tell us about your living conditions!

- before resettlement/ in Austria /after resettlement in Hungary

Work

- What is your current job; employed or self-employed, who do you work with (ethnicity), who are your bosses and subordinates? What are your working conditions?
- Does your current job match your professional qualifications?
- How would you rate your job situation? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

Housing conditions

- Tell us about the place where you live!
- How big is it, how many people live in it, how is it furnished and what is the neighbourhood like?
- How would you rate the situation of your apartment? Is it better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your living conditions?

Income

- How much is your monthly income now (in HUF, for you / your family you live with) - how do you measure this (previous income in Hungary / Austrians, immigrants, professional group, etc.)
- How do you consider your situation regarding your income? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect it to change in the future?

Wealth

- What noteworthy assets do you have (apartment, holiday home, car, business share)?
- Do you have any savings?
- How financially secure do you feel for the next two years?
- How would you assess your situation regarding your assets? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?

11 Overall satisfaction with life

Overall, how satisfied are you with your life now?

- How would you rate your situation in terms of satisfaction with life? Better or worse than? (compared to the reference group chosen by the respondent).
- How do you expect this to change in the future?
- How has the Covid epidemic affected your overall satisfaction with life?

12 Vision for the future

What do you think your personal future will be like, how will your career develop?

[What we want to know:

- What do they want, what do they aspire to, and what is realistic, what is most likely to happen to them?
- Where, what will their status be in 5-10 years, what will their citizenship be?

- Where and how do you envision your children's future? What social position will they achieve, where geographically, what kind of companion would they like to have by their side]?

End

(Say thank you and ask if she/he could recommend someone to be interviewed.)

2. Cognitive interviews

“The Austrian Academy of Sciences and Corvinus University of Budapest are conducting a sociological study on the subjective well-being and migration motivations of Hungarians living in Hungary and Austria. The title of the project is **MIGWELL**.

At this stage of the research, we are developing a questionnaire for a survey involving 300 participants. We would like to ask for your help with this. The interview will take approximately 1.5 hours, during which we will review the questionnaire together. We would like you to share your thoughts and feelings about each question.

To facilitate the analysis, the interview will be audio recorded. The recording will be treated confidentially; your name will not appear in the research analysis, and you will not be identifiable in any publication of the results.

You may stop the interview at any time, and you are free to skip any question you do not wish to answer. Please indicate that you agree to participate in the interview under these conditions.

Before we begin, please sign the **Consent Form**.”

2.1. Discussion of the questionnaire

[Information for the interviewer – not to be read aloud

The general objectives of the interview are:

- To understand how the respondent interprets the question — what the question and specific words mean to them.
- To explore how the respondent retrieves the information or memories needed to answer — what type of information is required, how it is recalled. Pay attention to the respondent’s level of motivation and concentration, whether the question is sensitive, and whether social desirability affects the answer (i.e., how truthful the response likely is).
- To check whether the respondent’s answer fits the available response options in the questionnaire.
- If the respondent wishes to revise an answer after reflection, accept and record the new answer.
- If the respondent selects “don’t know,” find out why and what conditions would allow them to give an answer.]

“Now I would like to go through the entire questionnaire with you. I will indicate which questions we should discuss in more detail. There are no right or wrong answers — we are interested in your personal opinions and how you interpret each question. If anything is unclear, not understandable, or if you encounter an unfamiliar word, please let me know!”

2.2. Basic socio-demographic data & “Filter questions”

address_at / address_hu – Is it clear what is meant by *permanent* and *temporary address*? Is the difference between the two understood?

country_pre – Refers to the place where you lived immediately before moving to Austria. Is it difficult to define this?

2.3. Spatial data

place_liv_pre / place_liv_pre_nuts2 – Do respondents know which county the settlement is/was in? Is there any issue with differences between permanent and temporary residence? (Either is acceptable for the survey.)

place_live – Is this a sensitive question for the respondent? Could it be sensitive for others? If so, why? Do they know which Austrian province the settlement belongs to?

2.4. Migration intention and decision

mighistory_why – Is the distinction between *reasons* and *goals* clear? Does the wording seem understandable and logical? How does the respondent decide which are their three most important factors? Is there anything important that was left out?

return_serious – *Alternative option*: Observe how quickly the respondent answers. If they hesitate, ask about the reason for the hesitation.

return_why / notreturn_why – Same as above: is the difference between *reasons* and *goals* clear? Is the wording logical? How are the top three factors chosen? Any missing options?

lived_up – How difficult is this question to answer? How does the respondent define “mostly”? Can they recall their expectations before moving abroad? Did those expectations change during their stay?

2.5. Objective indicators of well-being

hhsize_at – Is the short definition of *household* clear enough? Can they answer based on that?

legal_prop – How sensitive is this question? Are they willing to answer? Why might it be sensitive for others?

rooms – How do they define a *room*? Is the question clear enough to answer?

live_together – How complex is the question? What causes any uncertainty?

expenses – How did they interpret “usual expenses” and the categories (e.g., “easily” or “with difficulty”)?

debts – What does “burdensome” mean to them in this context?

unexp – How did they reach their answer? How do they define “unexpected”?

paybills – Is this question sensitive?

eatmeat – Do they find this question strange? (Clarify that it’s a standard Eurostat question.)

keepwarm – Are there aspects that make the answer uncertain? (e.g., heating the entire home or only certain rooms?) What temperature is considered “adequate”?

telephone / car / internet – Is “for personal use” clear? Are there situations where the question cannot be answered precisely?

remittances – Are there any factors that make this question unclear? If so, what?

remittances_perc – How difficult is it to quantify the amount of support?

educ_self – How does the respondent decide on self-classification? Especially for “no formal education” or “1–8 grades” — how are these understood?

selfconstat_3 – How does the respondent reach their self-assessment? Are the categories clear?

isco08_self / isco08_self_cat – How did they arrive at their answer? Did they respond quickly? If not, what caused hesitation? Was it easy to interpret the categories and choose one?

hours_work – Is it clear that this refers to *paid work*? How do they treat household work or unpaid work done for others?

overqualified – Is the term “qualification level” clear? (Emphasize that this refers to the *level* — basic, secondary, tertiary — not the *content* of qualification. For instance, if someone trained as a baker but works as a postman, that’s roughly the same level; but if a university graduate works as a postman, that’s a different level.)

health – Is this a sensitive question for them or for others?

partner – Are the terms *partnership* and *living with a partner* clear? (e.g., any kind of partner, regardless of legal status or cohabitation.)

marital – Are these categories clear? Do they treat them independently from their current situation? (e.g., if someone has a partner but isn’t married, they should officially select option 1.)

friends_at / friends_hu – How easy is it to count these people? How accurate is the answer — or is it just an approximation?

visit – Can the respondent clearly choose from the options? If not, why?

sociallex – What comes to mind when they read “being excluded from Austrian society”?

covid – Is it difficult to answer? If they hesitate, why? Is the wording appropriate?

ladder_pre / ladder_at / ladder_future – Is the question easy to interpret? How quickly do they answer? If slowly, why?

2.6. Subjective well-being

stf_overall – How difficult is it to give a single numeric answer about their overall life satisfaction?

stf..._pre – How hard is it to recall the period before migration? How accurate are those memories? Could the passage of time have changed their recollection of past circumstances and satisfaction?

Affective well-being – What do they think of the frequency categories? Are they clear? Do they adequately describe their experiences?

being_happy – What does *happiness* mean to the respondent when they answer this question?

meaningoflife – What comes to mind when asked about “meaningful activities”? Is it clear that the question is general, not only about work?

2.7. Trust

trust_others – Can the respondent provide a general answer? Is it clear that the question refers not only to Austrians but to people in general?

2.8. Final questions: monthly income

inc_p_1_pre / inc_h_1_pre – (Can be answered in HUF or EUR.) How does the respondent feel when faced with this question? How sensitive do they find it? Might it be difficult for others? When answering, is it challenging to define *income*? How do they calculate allowances or benefits (e.g., family allowance)? Record which income sources they include.

inc_p_1 / inc_h_1 – (To be answered in EUR only.) Same follow-up: How sensitive is the question? What makes it difficult? How do they include supplements and benefits? Record which income components are considered.

3. Survey questionnaire

Table of contents

1.	Info for the interviewers	51
2.	Alap szocio-demográfiai adatok és “szűrő kérdések” / Basic socio-demographic data & “Filter questions”	51
3.	Területi adatok / Spatial data	52
4.	Migrációs szándék és döntés / Migration intention and decision	54
5.	A jóllét objektív mutatói / Objective factors of well-being	57
5.1	Háztartás, lakhatási viszonyok / Household, housing conditions	57
5.2	Jövedelem és vagyon / Income and wealth.....	60
5.3	Képzettség és munka / Education and job	62
5.4	Egészségi állapot / Health condition.....	65
5.5	Szociális kapcsolatok / Social relationships	66
5.6	Szociális kirekesztődés / Social exclusion.....	69
5.7	Külső tényezők, külső összehasonlítás / External factors, external comparison.....	70
6.	Szubjektív jóllét / Subjective well-being	72
6.1	Elégedettség / Life satisfaction	72
6.2	Érzelmi, hangulati állapot / Affective well-being.....	73
6.3	Eudaimonikus jóllét / Eudaimonic well-being.....	74
7.	Bizalom / Trust	76
8.	Záró kérdések: havi jövedelem / Final questions: monthly income.....	77

FRONT PAGE (FOR THE ONLINE VERSION)

Tisztelt Hölgem/Uram!

Az Osztrák Tudományos Akadémia Urbanisztikai és Regionális Kutatások Intézete, illetve a Budapesti Corvinus Egyetem Empirikus Társadalomkutató Központja felmérést készít az Ausztriában élő magyarok jóllétéről és vándorlási motivációjáról. (A projekt címe: „Jóllét és migráció: a Magyarország - Ausztria migrációs kapcsolat” – MIGWELL, FWF I-5616).

Ehhez kapcsolódóan tennék fel kérdéseket a következő kb. 30-40 percben. Ha olyan kérdéshez ér, amelyre nem tudja a választ, vagy nem kíván rá válaszolni, minden esetben van lehetősége ezeket az opciókat választani. A kérdőív kitöltése bármikor szüneteltethető, és a későbbiekben ugyanonnan folytatható. (A válaszok automatikusan elmentődnek.) Ha bizonytalan valamely kérdéssel kapcsolatban, kollégánk bármikor szívesen áll a rendelkezésére.

A kérdőív kitöltése önkéntes és anonim módon történik. Az Ön személyes adatait (beleértve az Ön elérhetőségét) bizalmasan kezeljük az adatvédelmi törvényeknek megfelelően. Az adatok gyűjtése, elemzése, majd az eredmények publikálása során Ön semmilyen módon sem lesz beazonosítható.

Nagyon szépen köszönjük, hogy a kérdőív kitöltésével Ön is hozzájárul a kutatás sikerességéhez!

Üdvözlettel,

A MIGWELL csapat

Dear Sir/Madam!

The Institute for Urban and Regional Research of the Austrian Academy of Sciences and the Empirical Social Research Centre of the Corvinus University of Budapest are conducting a survey on the well-being and migration motivations of Hungarians living in Austria (project title: "Well-being and migration: the Hungary-Austria migration relationship" - MIGWELL, FWF I-5616).

We will ask questions related to this in the next 30-40 minutes. If you come to a question that you do not know the answer to or do not wish to answer, you will in any case have the possibility to choose one of these options. You can pause the questionnaire at any time and resume it from the same point later on. (Your answers will be automatically saved.) If you are unsure about any question, our colleagues will be happy to help you.

Completing the questionnaire is voluntary and anonymous. Your personal data (including your contact details) will be treated confidentially in accordance with data protection laws. You will not be identifiable in any way when the data is collected, analysed and the results published.

Thank you very much for your contribution to the success of the research by completing this questionnaire!

Best regards,

The MIGWELL team

Info for the interviewers

A kérdések után szerepelnek a változónevek (pl. *ybirth*). Ha egy kérdést nem mindenkitől kell kérdezni, a szűrés zölddel szerepel. / Variable names (e.g. *ybirth*) can be seen after the questions. If a question does not need to be asked from everyone, the filtering is shown in green.

Alap szocio-demográfiai adatok és “szűrő kérdések” / Basic socio-demographic data & “Filter questions”

Ön melyik évben született? / In which year were you born?

ybirth

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mi az Ön neme? / Gender

gender

1. Férfi / Male

2. Nő / Female

3. Egyén / Other

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön melyik országban született? / What country were you born in?

[Important: Hungary!]

cbirth_self

1. Magyarországon / Hungary

2. Egyéb, éspedig: ... / Other, namely: ...

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Rendelkezik-e Ön bejelentett lakcímmel Ausztriában? (Meldezettel-ben: állandó vagy ideiglenes lakcím, azaz Hauptwohnsitz vagy Nebenwohnsitz) / Do you have a registered address in Austria? (Meldezettel: permanent or temporary, ie. Hauptwohnsitz or Nebenwohnsitz) [Important: must have] *address_at*

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem / No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Rendelkezik-e Ön bejelentett lakcímmel Magyarországon? (Lakcímkártyán: állandó vagy tartózkodási cím) / Do you have a registered address in Hungary? (Residence card: permanent or temporary) *address_hu*

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem / No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön melyik évben költözött Ausztriába? / In which year did you move to Austria? [Important: between 1990 and 2022] *yimmig*

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön életvitelszerűen melyik országban élt közvetlenül azelőtt, hogy Ausztriába költözött? / Which country did you live in before moving to Austria? [Important: Hungary] *country_pre*

1. Magyarországon / In Hungary
2. Egyéb országban, éspedig: ... / In another country, namely: ...
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Területi adatok / Spatial data

Önnek mely településen, illetve megyében van (vagy volt a legutóbbi) lakcíme Magyarországon? / Which settlement and county do you have (or did you have the last) address in Hungary?

Település / Settlement: _____

place_liv_pre

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Megye / County:

place_liv_pre_nuts2

1. BUDAPEST
 2. Bács-Kiskun
 3. Baranya
 4. Békés
 5. Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén
 6. Csongrád-Csanád
 7. Fejér
 8. Győr-Moson-Sopron
 9. Hajdú-Bihar
 10. Heves
 11. Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok
 12. Komárom-Esztergom
 13. Nógrád
 14. Pest (Budapesten kívül)
 15. Somogy
 16. Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg
 17. Tolna
 18. Vas
 19. Veszprém
 20. Zala
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

**Ön jelenleg melyik településen, illetve tartományban él életvitelszerűen Ausztriában? /
Which Austrian settlement and federal province are you currently living in?**

Település / Settlement: _____

place_live

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Tartomány / Federal province:

Nuts2

1. Burgenland
2. Kärnten
3. Steiermark
4. Niederösterreich
5. Oberösterreich
6. Salzburg

7. Tirol
8. Vorarlberg
9. Wien
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Migrációs szándék és döntés / Migration intention and decision

Milyen célból vagy okból döntött az Ausztriába költözés mellett? Kérjük, legfeljebb 3 választ jelöljön! / What were your reasons or objectives for moving to Austria? Please mark a maximum of 3 answers!

mighistory_why

1. Anyagi, megélhetési okból. / Financial reasons.
2. Jobb munkafeltételek miatt. / Better standards of work.
3. Kiszámíthatóbb jövőkép miatt. / More predictable future. keep
4. Szakmai okból (karrier lehetősége, tapasztalatszerzés). / Professional reasons (career, experience).
5. Tanulmányi okból (jobb képzés, nyelvgyakorlás, külföldi diploma megszerzése). / Educational reasons (better training, language learning, earning a foreign degree).
6. Személyes kapcsolatok miatt (családi ok, barátok stb.). / Because of personal relations (family reasons, friends etc.).
7. Politikai, ideológiai okból. / Political, ideological reasons.
8. A közszolgáltatások színvonala és megbízhatósága miatt (egészségügy, oktatás, bürokrácia stb.). / The quality and reliability of public service (health, education, bureaucracy, etc.).
9. A közbiztonság miatt. / Public safety.
10. A magyarországi jövőm anyagi megalapozása céljából (pl. családalapítás, házépítés, vállalkozás indítása Magyarországon). / To financially secure my future in Hungary (e.g. starting a family, building a house, starting a business in Hungary).
11. Egyéb, éspedig: ... / Other, namely: ...
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Tervezi-e, hogy a következő 3 évben visszaköltözik Magyarországra? / Do you plan to move back to Hungary in the next 3 years?

return

- 1: Igen / Yes
- 2: Nem / No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(If: *return* = 2. Ha a fenti válasz “igen”): A Magyarországra visszaköltözéssel kapcsolatos terveire a következők közül melyik igaz leginkább? / (If: *return* = 2. If the answer was “yes”): Which of the following statements is the most accurate about your plans to return to Hungary?

return_serious

- 1: Még csak fontolgatom a lehetőséget. / I am still considering the possibility.
- 2: Komolyan foglalkozom a gondolattal. / I am seriously considering the idea.
- 3: Már meghoztam a döntést. / I have already made the decision.
- 4: Már konkrét lépéseket is tettem. / I have already taken concrete steps.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(If: *return* = 2. Ha a fenti válasz “igen”): Milyen célból vagy okból tervezi, hogy visszaköltözik Magyarországra? Kérjük, legfeljebb 3 választ jelöljön! / (If: *return* = 2. If the answer was “yes”): What are your reasons or objectives for returning to Hungary? Please mark a maximum of 3 answers!

return_why

1. Anyagi, megélhetési okból. / Financial reasons.
2. Jobb munkafeltételek miatt. / Better standards of work.
3. Kiszámíthatóbb jövőkép miatt. / More predictable future.
4. Szakmai okból (karrier lehetősége, tapasztalatszerzés). / Professional reasons (career, experience).
5. Tanulmányi okból (jobb képzés, nyelvgyakorlás, magyar diploma megszerzése). / Educational reasons (better training, language learning, earning a Hungarian degree).
6. Személyes kapcsolatok miatt (családi ok, barátok stb.). / Because of personal relations (family reasons, friends etc.).
7. Politikai, ideológiai okból. / Political, ideological reasons.
8. A közszolgáltatások színvonala és megbízhatósága miatt (egészségügy, oktatás, bürokrácia stb.). / The quality and reliability of public service (health, education, bureaucracy, etc.).
9. A közbiztonság miatt. / Public safety.
12. Teljesült a kiköltözéskor kitűzött célom. / I have achieved what I wanted to achieve abroad.
13. Nem sikerült megszoknom az ausztriai életet. / I couldn't accustom to living in Austria.
11. Egyéb, éspedig: ... / Other, namely: ...
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(If: return = 1. Ha a fenti válasz “nem”): Mi az oka annak, hogy NEM kíván visszaköltözni Magyarországra? Kérjük, legfeljebb 3 választ jelöljön! / (If: return = 1. Ha a fenti válasz “nem”): What are the reasons for NOT returning to Hungary? Please mark a maximum of 3 answers!

notreturn_why

1. Anyagi, megélhetési okból. / Financial reasons.
2. Jobb munkafeltételek miatt. / Better standards of work.
3. Kiszámíthatóbb jövőkép miatt. / More predictable future.
4. Szakmai okból (karrier lehetősége, tapasztalatszerzés). / Professional reasons (career, experience).
5. Tanulmányi okból (jobb képzés, nyelvgyakorlás, külföldi diploma megszerzése). / Educational reasons (better training, language learning, earning a foreign degree).
6. Személyes kapcsolatok miatt (családi ok, barátok stb.). / Because of personal relations (family reasons, friends etc.).
7. Politikai, ideológiai okból. / Political, ideological reasons.
8. A közszolgáltatások színvonala és megbízhatósága miatt (egészségügy, oktatás, bürokrácia stb.). / The quality and reliability of public service (health, education, bureaucracy, etc.).
9. A közbiztonság miatt. / Public safety.
14. Még nem teljesült a kiköltözéskor kitűzött célom. / I haven't achieved yet what I wanted to achieve abroad.
11. Egyéb, éspedig: ... / Other, namely: ...
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Tervezi-e, hogy a következő 2 éven belül egy másik országba (de nem Magyarországra) költözik munka, tanulás vagy egyéb okból? / Do you plan to move to another country (but not Hungary) in the next 2 years for work, study or other reasons?

migintention

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem /No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön szerint az Ausztriába költözése összességében véve beváltotta-e azokat a reményeket, elvárásokat, amiket a költözés előtt remélt vagy elvárt? / Overall, do you think that your move to Austria has lived up to the hopes and expectations you had before the move?

lived_up

- 5: Igen, teljesen beváltotta a reményeket. / Yes, it completely lived up to expectations.
- 4: Igen, nagyrészt beváltotta a reményeket. / Yes, it largely lived up to expectations.

- 3: Vegyes: igen is, és nem is. / Mixed: Yes and no.
 2: Nem, nagyrészt nem váltotta be a reményeket. / No, it has largely failed to meet expectations.
 1: Nem, egyáltalán nem váltotta be a reményeket. / No, it has not fulfilled expectations at all.
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

A jóllét objektív mutatói / Objective factors of well-being

3.1 Háztartás, lakhatási viszonyok / Household, housing conditions

Mi a háztartás?

Egy háztartást olyan személyek alkotnak, akik egy lakásban vagy annak egy részében **együtt laknak, és a létfenntartás költségeit – legalább részben – közösen viselik** (pl. az étkezést, a napi kiadásokat). A háztartás tagjai közé az eltartott személyek is beleszámítanak.

Az Ausztriában élő magyarok közül sokan **két háztartásnak is tagjai**: egy háztartást fenntartanak Magyarországon (gyakran a családjuk többi tagja ott él), és egy háztartást fenntartanak Ausztriában is. Ha Önre is igaz ez, kérjük, hogy mindkét háztartásra vonatkozóan válaszolja meg az alábbi kérdést!

*(Megjegyzés: Ha Ön albérlőtársakkal él együtt, és kizárólag a lakbért fizetik közösen, akkor ez **egyszemélyes háztartásnak** minősül. Szintén egyszemélyes a háztartás, ha Ön egyedül él, és például egy hotelben kap szállást a munkáltatójától.*

What is a household?

A household is made up of persons who **live together** in a dwelling or part of a dwelling and **share at least part of the household's expenses** (e.g. food, daily expenses). Dependent persons are also members of the household.

Many Hungarians living in Austria are **members of two households**: one in Hungary (often with other members of their family living there) and one in Austria. If this applies to you, please answer the question below accordingly!

*Note: If you live with tenants and only pay rent together, this is a **one-person household**. It is also a one-person household if you live alone, and get accommodation from your employer e.g. in a hotel.*

Összesen hány fő él az Ön háztartásában? / How many people are living in your household?

Ausztriában / In Austria: _____ fő / person

hhsiz_e_at

Magyarországon (ha van): / In Hungary (if has) _____ fő / persons (Önt is beleértve / including You) *hhsize_hu*

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Milyen jogcímen él az ausztriai ingatlanban? / What is your legal relationship to the property? *legal_prop*

1. A lakás tulajdonosa (haszonélvezője), vagy annak házastársa, élettársa, rokona vagyok. / I am the owner (beneficial owner) of the dwelling, or its spouse, partner or relative.
2. Az egész lakást bérelem, vagy a bérlő házastársa, élettársa, rokona vagyok. / I rent the whole dwelling or I am the spouse, partner or relative of the tenant.
3. A lakás egy részét bérelem. / I rent part of the dwelling.
4. Kereskedelmi szálláshelyen élek (pl. hotelben, panzióban). / I live in commercial accommodation (e.g. hotel, boarding house)
5. Egyéb intézetben, pl. kollégiumban, munkásszálláson, egészségügyi otthonban, szociális otthonban élek. / I live in other accommodation, e.g. in a dormitory, workhouse, health home, social home.
6. Egyéb, éspedig: / Other, namely:

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Összesen hány szobás a lakás, amelyben a háztartásával Ausztriában lakik (a nappalival együtt, de a konyha és a fürdőszoba nélkül)? A félszoba szobának számít, és az „amerikai konyha” – nappali és konyha funkció összekapcsolva – is egy szobának számít. / Total number of rooms in the dwelling your household lives in Austria (with the living room but without the kitchen and bathroom)? The half-room counts as a room, and the "American kitchen" - living room and kitchen function combined - also counts as a room.

rooms

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Jellemző-e az alábbi problémák bármelyike a lakásra, amiben Ausztriában lakik, vagy annak lakóköznyezetére? / Are any of the following problems common to the Austrian dwelling you live in or its living environment?

1. Igen / Yes

2. Nem /No

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

A lakás mennyezete/falazata/padlója/alapja beázik, nedvesedik, penészedik? / Is the ceiling/plaster/flooring/foundation of your home leaking, damp, mouldy? <i>leaking_at</i>	1 2 98 99
A lakás nem elég világos, a szobák sötétek? / The apartment is not bright enough, the rooms are dark <i>dark_at</i>	1 2 98 99
Zajosak a szomszédok, vagy nagy zaj szűrődik be az utcáról? / Noisy neighbours or loud noise from the street <i>noise_at</i>	1 2 98 99
Szennyezés, por, egyéb környezeti probléma (pl. füst, bűz, korom, szennyezett víz)? / Pollution, dust, other environmental problems (e.g. smoke, stench, soot, contaminated water) <i>env_problem_at</i>	1 2 98 99
Rossz közbiztonság, vandalizmus? / Poor public security, vandalism? <i>crime_at</i>	1 2 98 99

Ön kivel él egy lakásban Ausztriában? Több válasz is megjelölhető. Kérjük adja meg azt is, hogy hány főről van szó az adott kategóriában! (Például hány 6 éven aluli gyermekkel él együtt?) / Who do you live together in a flat in Austria? You can tick more than one answer. Please also indicate the number of persons in each category! (E.g. how many children under 6 years of age live with you?)

live_together

1. Egyedül élek. / I live alone.
2. Házastársammal, élettársammal vagy partneremmel / My spouse or partner
_____ fő / persons
3. 6 éven aluli gyermekemmel (vagy a párom gyermekével) / My child (or the child of
my partner), below 6 years old _____ fő / persons
4. 6-18 év közötti gyermekemmel (vagy a párom gyermekével) / My child (or the child
of my partner), between 6 – 18 years old _____ fő / persons
5. 18 éven felüli gyermekemmel (vagy a párom gyermekével) / My child (or the child
of my partner), above 18 years old _____ fő / persons
6. Szülőmmel (vagy a párom szülőjével) / My parent (or my partner's parent)
_____ fő / persons
7. Testvéremmel (vagy a párom testvérével) / My sister or brother (or my partner's
sister or brother) _____ fő / persons
8. Egyéb rokonommal / Other of my relatives _____ fő / persons
9. Barátommal, munkatársammal / Friends, colleagues _____ fő / persons
10. Egyéb személlyel / Other persons. _____ fő / persons
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

3.2 Jövedelem és vagyon / Income and wealth

Véleménye szerint hogyan tudja fedezni az Ön háztartása a szokásos kiadásokat (beleértve a hiteleket is)? / How do you think your household can cover its usual expenses (including loans)?

expenses

1. Nagy nehézségek árán / With major difficulties
2. Nehézségek árán / With difficulties
3. Kisebbs nehézségek árán / With some difficulties
4. Viszonylag könnyen / Rather easily
5. Könnyen / Easily
6. Nagyon könnyen / Very easily
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Képes volna-e a háztartás arra, hogy egy váratlan, nagyobb összegű (1290 eurós) kiadást a saját forrásaiból fedezzen? / Household capacity to face unexpected expenses (1,290 EUR).

unexp

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem /No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Megengedhetik-e maguknak, hogy évente legalább egy hétre elmenjenek nyaralni? / Household capacity to afford paying for one week annual holiday away from home.

holiday

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem /No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Előfordult-e az utóbbi 12 hónapban, hogy pénzhiány miatt nem tudták határidőre befizetni a lakbért, a közös költséget, valamilyen közüzemi díjat, vagy valamilyen hitel törlesztőrészletét? / Household capacity to being confronted with payment arrears (on mortgage or rental payments, utility bills, hire purchase instalments or other loan payments)

paybills

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem /No
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Megengedhetik-e maguknak, hogy legalább minden második nap húst, vagy annak megfelelő vegetáriánus ételt fogyasszanak? / Household capacity to afford a meat, chicken, fish or vegetarian equivalent every second day. *eatmeat*

1. Igen / Yes

2. Nem /No

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Megengedhetik-e maguknak, hogy a lakásukat megfelelően fűtsék? / Household capacity to keep home adequately warm. *keepwarm*

1. Igen / Yes

2. Nem /No

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Van-e a háztartása használatában (személyes használatra)? / Which of the following assets does your household have for personal use?

3: Igen

2: Nincs, mert nem engedhetem meg magamnak. / No, because I cannot afford it.

1: Nincs, egyéb okból. / No, other reason.

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Vezetékes vagy mobiltelefon / Landline or mobile phone <i>telephone</i>	3 2 1 98 99
Színes televízió (LCD, Plazma is) / Color TV (LCD, plasma too) <i>television</i>	3 2 1 98 99
Mosógép / Washing machine <i>washingmachine</i>	3 2 1 98 99
Személygépkocsi (személyes használatra)? / Car (for personal use) <i>car</i>	3 2 1 98 99
Internet / Internet <i>internet</i>	3 2 1 98 99

Támogatja Ön anyagilag az ausztriai jövedelméből valamely Magyarországon élő családtagját vagy családtagjait? / Do you financially support a family member living in Hungary from Austria? *remittances*

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem /No
3. Nincs Magyarországon élő családtagom. / I don't have relatives in Hungary.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

A havi jövedelmének átlagosan körülbelül mekkora hányadát utalja Magyarországra, vagy használja fel Magyarországon? / What percentage of your monthly income do you usually transfer to Hungary or spend in Hungary? *remittances_perc*

kb. / ca. _____ százalékát / percentage

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

3.3 Képzettség és munka / Education and job

Mi az Ön legmagasabb befejezett iskolai végzettsége? / What is your highest completed level of education? *educ_self*

1. Nincs iskolai végzettségem / No education
2. Alapfokú: általános iskola, 1-8. osztály / Primary: primary school, grades 1-8
3. Középfokú: szakiskolai, szakmunkásképző bizonyítvány / Secondary: vocational school, vocational certificate
4. Középfokú: érettségi bizonyítvány szakképesítés nélkül vagy szakképesítéssel / Secondary: school leaving certificate without or with vocational qualification
5. Felsőfokú: felsőfokú szakképesítő bizonyítvány, főiskolai vagy egyetemi diploma, tudományos (PhD- vagy DLA-) fokozat / Tertiary: higher vocational certificate, college or university diploma, scientific (PhD or DLA) degree
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Gazdasági aktivitás szempontjából Ön elsődlegesen mely csoportba tartozik jelenleg? / In terms of economic activity, which group do you currently belong to?

selfeconstat_3

1. Alkalmazott a közszférában / Employee in the public sector.
2. Alkalmazott a magánszférában. / Employee in the private sector.
3. Vállalkozó/ Entrepreneur
4. Saját vagy családi vállalkozásban dolgozom / Work in own or family business
5. Munkanélküli, álláskereső / Unemployed
6. Tanuló, hallgató / Student

7. Saját jogon nyugdíjas / Retired
8. Rokkantsági, rehabilitációs ellátásban részesülők / Disabled
9. Egyéb inaktív (gyermekgondozási ellátást kap; ápolási díjban részesül; vagyonából, ingatlan-bérbeadásból élő; háztartásbeli; szociális segélyezett; hozzátartozói jogon nyugdíjas, járadékos;) / Other inactive (in receipt of childcare benefits; in receipt of care allowance; living on property, renting property; householder; on social assistance; pensioner by right of dependency)
10. Alkalmi munkát, megbízásokat vállalok / Take on occasional works
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mi az Ön munkája, foglalkozása jelenleg? (Ha most nincs: amikor utoljára dolgozott, mi volt a munkája?) / What is your current profession? (If you don't have now: When you worked last time, what was your last profession?) *isco08_self*

0: Jelenleg nincs munkám, és korábban sem volt. / Currently I don't have job, and I did not have previously.

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(Ha van, vagy volt valaha munkája. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Az Ön munkája, foglalkozása az alábbiak közül melyik kategóriába sorolható be? (Ha most nincs munkája: akkor a legutolsó munkája hová sorolható be?) / (If has or had a job. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Which category does your current profession fit into? (If you don't have now: When you worked last time, which category did your current profession fit into?) *isco08_self_cat*

1. Gazdasági, igazgatási, érdekképviselési vezető, törvényhozó
2. Felsőfokú képzettség önálló alkalmazását igénylő foglalkozás
3. Egyéb felsőfokú vagy középfokú képzettséget igénylő foglalkozás
4. Irodai és ügyviteli (ügyfélkapcsolati) foglalkozás
5. Kereskedelmi és szolgáltatási foglalkozás
6. Mezőgazdasági és erdőgazdálkodási foglalkozás
7. Ipari és építőipari foglalkozás
8. Gépkészítő, összeszerelő, járművezető
9. Szakképzettséget nem igénylő foglalkozás
0. Fegyveres szervek foglalkozása
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(Ha van, vagy volt valaha munkája. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Ön hány órát dolgozik általában egy héten? (Ha most nincs munkája: hány órát dolgozott hetente az utolsó munkahelyén?) / (If has or had a job. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). How many hours do you regularly work per week? (If you don't have now: how many hours did you work per week in your last job?)
hours_work

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(Ha van, vagy volt valaha munkája. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Milyen időtartamra szól a munkaszerződése? (Ha most nincs munkája: utoljára milyen időtartamra szól?) / (If has or had a job. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). What is the duration of your employment contract? (If you don't have now: what was the duration of your last contract?)
contract

1. Határozott idejű, 6 hónapnál rövidebb időre szóló / Fixed term, less than 6 months

2. Határozott idejű, 6 hónapnál hosszabb időre szóló / Fixed term, more than 6 months

3. Határozatlan idejű / Permanent (indefinite)

4. Nincs hivatalos munkaszerződésem / No formal employment contract

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(Ha van, vagy volt valaha munkája. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0) + (Ha nem vállalkozó. If *selfeconstat_3* ≠ 3.): A munkahelyén van-e lehetősége arra, hogy magasabb beosztásba kerüljön, vagy nagyobb önállósága legyen? (Illetve amikor utoljára dolgozott, volt-e lehetősége erre?) / (If has or had a job. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0) + (If not entrepreneur. If *selfeconstat_3* ≠ 3): Does your workplace offer you the opportunity to move up to a higher position or to have more autonomy? (Or, when you last worked, did you have the opportunity to do so?)
higherpos

1. Egyáltalán nem. / Not at all.

2. Inkább nem. / Rather no.

3. Inkább igen. / Rather yes.

4. Egyértelműen igen. / Yes, absolutely.

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(Ha van, vagy volt valaha munkája. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Ön a képzettségi szintjéhez (alap-, közép- vagy felsőfokú) viszonyítva milyen jellegű munkát végez Ausztriában? / (If has or had a job. If *isco08_self* ≠ 0). Compared to your level of education (primary, secondary or tertiary), what kind of work are you doing in Austria?
overqualified

1. A képzettségi szintemnek megfelelő munkát végzek. / A work that is adequate for my level of education.
2. A képzettségi szintemhez képest alacsonyabb szintű munkát végzek. / A work that is below my level of education.
3. A képzettségi szintemhez képest magasabb szintű munkát végzek. / A work that is above my level of education.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön milyen szinten beszél németül, mennyire képes másokat megérteni, és magát megértetni? / What is your level of German, your ability to understand others and to make yourself understood? *german*

- 1: Semennyire / Not at all.
- 2: Alapszinten / Basic level
- 3: Társalgási szinten / Level of conversation
- 4: Haladó szinten / Advanced level
- 5: Anyanyelvi szinten / Native level
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

3.4 Egészségi állapot / Health condition

Hogyan jellemezné általános egészségi állapotát? / How is your health in general? Is it... *health*

- 1: Nagyon rossz / Very bad
- 2: Rossz / Bad
- 3: Kielégítő / Fair
- 4: Jó / Good
- 5: Nagyon jó / Very good
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Az elmúlt legalább 6 hónapban korlátozta-e Önt valamilyen egészségi probléma a mindennapi tevékenységek elvégzésében, és ha igen, akkor milyen mértékben? / In at least the past six months, to what extent have you been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? *restriction*

- 1: Nem, egyáltalán nem korlátozta / No, not restricted at all
- 2: Igen, kis mértékben korlátozta / Yes, slightly restricted

- 3: Igen, jelentős mértékben korlátozta / Yes, strongly restricted
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

3.5 Szociális kapcsolatok / Social relationships

Ön jelenleg párkapcsolatban él? Ez vonatkozhat házastársra, élettársra, vagy nem hivatalos párkapcsolatra is. / Do you live currently in a relationship? This can apply to a spouse, cohabiting partner or non-official partnership. *partner*

- 1: Igen / Yes
- 2: Nem / No
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

(If partner = 2. Ha “igen”): az Ön párja milyen nemzetiségű? / (If partner = 2. If “yes”): what is your partner’s nationality? *partner_nat*

- 1. Magyar / Hungarian
- 2. Osztrák / Austrian
- 3. Egyéb, éspedig: ... / Other, namely: ...
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mi az Ön családi állapota? / What is your marital status? *marital*

- 1. Hajadon/nőtlen (soha nem is volt házas) / Single (never married)
- 2. Házas / Married
- 3. Özvegy / Widowed
- 4. Elvált / Divorced
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Önnek hány eltartott (saját jövedelemmel nem rendelkező) gyermeke van? / How many dependent children (without own income) do you have? *children*

Vannak-e olyan rokonai, barátai vagy ismerősei Ausztriában, illetve Magyarországon, akik nem az Ön háztartásában élnek, és akiktől szükség esetén anyagi vagy nem anyagi jellegű segítséget kérhet? (Nem anyagi segítség például: tanácskérés, lelki támasz,

gyerekefelügyelet, technikai segítség, ügyintézés stb.) Több válasz is megjelölhető. / Overall, do you feel that you could receive material or non-material help / social support from relatives, friends, acquaintances (outside your household in Austria and/or Hungary) if you need it? (Non-material help, for example: advice, emotional support, childcare, technical assistance, administration, etc.) You can tick more than one answer.

1. Igen, vannak olyanok AUSZTRIÁBAN, akiktől ANYAGI jellegű segítséget kérhetek. / Yes, I could receive material help from people in Austria. *help_material_at*
2. Igen, vannak olyanok MAGYARORSZÁGON, akiktől ANYAGI jellegű segítséget kérhetek. / Yes, I could receive material help from people in Hungary. *help_material_hu*
3. Igen, vannak olyanok AUSZTRIÁBAN, akiktől NEM ANYAGI jellegű segítséget kérhetek. / Yes, I could receive non-material help / social support from people in Austria. *help_nonmaterial_at*
4. Igen, vannak olyanok MAGYARORSZÁGON, akiktől NEM ANYAGI jellegű segítséget kérhetek. / Yes, I could receive non-material help / social support from people in Hungary. *help_nonmaterial_hu*
5. Nem, nincsenek olyanok, akiktől anyagi vagy nem anyagi jellegű segítséget kérhetnék. / No, I could not receive any material help or social support.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

A családján kívül hány olyan személy van, akivel meg tudja beszélni a személyes, bizalmas dolgait? / Not counting your family, how many people are there with whom you can discuss intimate and personal matters?

Ausztriában? <i>friends_at</i>	_____	98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.	99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.
Magyarországon? <i>friends_hu</i>	_____	98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.	99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

A barátai, ismerősei többségében milyen nemzetiségűek Ausztriában? / What are the nationalities of your friends and acquaintances in Austria? *friends_nat*

0. Egyáltalán nincsenek barátaim és ismerőseim Ausztriában. / I don't have friends and acquaintances in Austria at all.
1. Inkább magyarok. / Rather Hungarians.
2. Inkább osztrákok. / Rather Austrians.

3. Inkább más nemzetiségűek. / Rather other nationalities.
4. Vegyesen magyarok, osztrákok és más nemzetiségűek. / Mixed: Hungarians, Austrians and other nationalities.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Jár Ön rendszeresen moziba, színházba, edzésre, illetve részt vesz hasonló szabadidős programon, ami pénzbe kerül? / Do you regularly engage in leisure activities if they involve costs, e.g. sports, going to the cinema, concerts or pubs? *leisure*

- 3: Igen
- 2: Nem, mert nem engedhetem meg magamnak. / No, because I cannot afford it.
- 1: Nem, egyéb okból. / No, other reason.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Szokott-e Ön a barátaival, rokonaival havonta legalább egyszer találkozni, hogy együtt megegyenek vagy megigyanak valamit? / Do you meet friends or relatives at least once a month to have a drink or a meal together? *meet_friends*

- 3: Igen
- 2: Nem, mert nem engedhetem meg magamnak. / No, because I cannot afford it.
- 1: Nem, egyéb okból. / No, other reason.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Milyen gyakran, milyen rendszeresen látogatótt Magyarországra az elmúlt 12 hónapban (személyes okokból, például családi, baráti látogatás céljából)? / How often, how frequently did you visit Hungary in the past 12 months (for personal reasons, for example to visit family or friends)? *visit*

1. Havonta többször / Several times a month
2. Havonta egyszer / Once a month
3. 2–3 havonta / Once every 2–3 months
4. 1–2 alkalommal / 1–2 times
5. Egyáltalán nem voltam Magyarországon ebben az időszakban / I did not visit Hungary at all in this period
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Az emberek különböző csoportokhoz, önkéntes szervezetekhez tartozhatnak. Jelenleg tagja-e Ön valamilyen szociális, jótékonyági, egyházi, politikai, szakszervezeti, sport, vagy kulturális szervezetnek Ausztriában? / People can belong to different groups, voluntary organisations. Are you or have you been a member of any social, charity, religious, political, trade union, sport or cultural organisations in Austria? civic_at

1. Igen, tagja vagyok egy vagy több ausztriai magyar kulturális egyesületnek. / Yes, I am a member of a Hungarian cultural association in Austria.
2. Igen, tagja vagyok valamilyen más – szociális, jótékonyági, egyházi, politikai, szakszervezeti, sport, vagy kulturális – szervezet(ek)nek Ausztriában. / Yes, I am a member of some other organisation(s) - social, charitable, ecclesiastical, political, trade union, sport or cultural - in Austria.
3. Nem vagyok tagja semmilyen egyesületnek Ausztriában. / I am not a member of any association in Austria.
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ausztriában a helyi önkormányzati választásokon minden állandó lakcímmel rendelkező EU-állampolgár szavazhat. Szavazna-e Ön a következő helyi önkormányzati választáson Ausztriában? / In Austria, all EU citizens with a permanent address can vote in local elections. Do you plan to vote in the next local elections in Austria? vote

1. Igen / Yes
2. Nem / No
- 0: Nincs állandó lakcímem Ausztriában (csak tartózkodási címem van). / I don't have permanent address in Austria (only temporary address).
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

3.6 Szociális kirekesztődés / Social exclusion

Az alábbiakban néhány állítást olvasok fel Önnek. Mennyire ért egyet az alábbi állításokkal? / I will now read out a statement to you. Do you fully agree, tend to agree, neither agree, tend to disagree or not at all?

Ön kirekesztve érzi magát az osztrák társadalomból... / You feel excluded from the Austrian society... sociallex

- 1: Teljesen mértékben egyetértek / I totally agree.
- 2: Inkább egyetértek / Rather agree.
- 3: Részben igen, részben nem értek egyet / partly agree, partly disagree.
- 4: Inkább nem értek egyet / Rather disagree.

- 5: Egyáltalán nem értek egyet / Strongly disagree.
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Ön úgy érzi, hogy néhány ember lenézi Önt Ausztriában a munkája vagy a jövedelmi helyzete miatt... / You feel that some people in Austria look down on you because of your working or income situation... *looked_down*

- 1: Teljesen mértékben egyetértek / I totally agree.
- 2: Inkább egyetértek / Rather agree.
- 3: Részben igen, részben nem értek egyet / partly agree, partly disagree.
- 4: Inkább nem értek egyet / Rather disagree.
- 5: Egyáltalán nem értek egyet / Strongly disagree.
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Külső tényezők, külső összehasonlítás / External factors, external comparison

Mennyire érzi biztonságban magát, ha egyedül sétál az ausztriai lakóhelye környékén sötétedés után? / How safe do you feel walking alone around your home in Austria after dark? *feelsafe*

- 4: Nagyon biztonságban érzem magam. / I feel very safe.
- 3: Elégge biztonságban érzem magam. / I feel quite safe.
- 2: Egy kicsit veszélyben érzem magam. / I feel a little bit safe.
- 1: Egyáltalán nem érzem magam biztonságban. / I don't feel safe at all.
- 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
- 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Hogyan befolyásolta a Covid-19 pandémia az Ön életét? / How has the Covid-19 pandemic affected your life? *covid*

- 1. Súlyos gondokat okozott / It caused serious problems
- 2. Kiseb gondokat okozott / It caused some problems
- 3. Nem okozott különösebb gondokat / Did not cause any particular problems
- 4. Egyáltalán nem okozott gondokat / Did not cause any problems at all
- 5. Inkább pozitív hatása volt / It had a rather positive impact
- 98. Nem tudja. / Don't know.
- 99. Nem kíván válaszolni. / Don't want to answer.

Igazak-e Önre az alábbi állítások? A Covid-19 pandémia miatt... / Due to the Covid-19 pandemic...

		Igen/ Yes	Nem / No	Nem tudja. / Don't know.	Nem kíván válaszolni. / Don't want to answer.
<i>covid_job</i>	...elvesztette-e állását? / ... have you lost your job?	1	2	98	99
<i>covid_inc</i>	...csökkent-e a jövedelme? / ... has your income decreased?	1	2	98	99
<i>covid_health</i>	...tartósan romlott-e egészségügyi állapota? / ... have you contracted long covid?	1	2	98	99
<i>covid_return</i>	...haza kellett-e költöznie külföldről Magyarországra? / ... have you had to move back to Hungary from abroad?	1	2	98	99
<i>covid_emig</i>	... külföldre kellett-e költöznie Magyarországról? / ... have you had to move abroad from Hungary?	1	2	98	99

Különböző társadalmi helyzetű, életvitelű emberek vannak a társadalomban. Képzelsen el egy létrát, aminek a felső foka a társadalom felső részét, az alsó foka pedig az alsó részét jelenti. Kérjük, értékelje 0-tól 10-ig, hogy... / There are people in society with different social positions and lifestyles. Imagine a ladder with the upper level representing the upper part of society and the lower level representing the lower part. Please rate from 0 to 10 that:

- **Az Ausztriába költözés előtt Ön a létra melyik fokán állt Magyarországon? / Before moving to Austria, which rung of the ladder were you on in Hungary?**
ladder_pre

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

- **Jelenleg hol helyezné el Önmagát a létrán Ausztriában? / Where would you currently place yourself on the ladder in Austria?**
ladder_at

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

- **Mire számít, hol fog Ön elhelyezkedni ezen a létrán 5 év múlva? / Where do you expect to be on this ladder in 5 years?**
ladder_future

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Szubjektív jóllét / Subjective well-being

3.1 Elégedettség / Life satisfaction

Összességében mennyire elégedett Ön ...? / Overall, how satisfied are you...?

0. egyáltalán nem elégedett, 10. teljes mértékben elégedett /

0. Not at all satisfied, 10. Completely satisfied

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

... az életével általában? / with your life in general? <i>stf_overall</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a saját jövedelmével? / your own income? <i>stf_income</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a háztartása anyagi helyzetével? / your household's financial situation? <i>stf_financial</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakásával? / your accommodation? <i>stf_accommodation</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a jelenlegi munkájával? / your current job? <i>stf_job</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... az egészségi állapotával? / your health? <i>stf_health</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a személyes kapcsolataival? / your personal relationships? <i>stf_relation</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... azon idő mennyiségével, amelyet az Ön által kedvelt dolgokkal tölthet? / the amount of time you can spend doing the things you like? <i>stf_timeuse</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakókörnyezete minőségével? / the quality of your living environment? <i>stf_livingenv</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakókörnyezetében sportolásra, pihenésre rendelkezésre álló helyekkel és zöldterületekkel? / recreational or green areas in your living area? <i>stf_greenarea</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a közszolgáltatások (egészségügy, oktatás, bürokrácia stb.) minőségével, megbízhatóságával, elérhetőségével? / quality, reliability, accessibility of public services (healthcare system, education system, bureaucracy etc.)? <i>stf_public</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Most gondoljon vissza az Ausztriába költözés előtti időszakra! Összességében mennyire volt elégedett Ön ... / Now think back to the year before you moved to Austria! Overall, how satisfied were you...

0. egyáltalán nem elégedett, 10. teljes mértékben elégedett /

0. Not at all satisfied, 10. Completely satisfied

... az életével általában? / with your life in general? <i>stf_overall_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a saját jövedelmével? / your own income? <i>stf_income_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a háztartása anyagi helyzetével? / your household's financial situation? <i>stf_financial_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakásával? / your accommodation? <i>stf_accommodation_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... az akkori munkájával? / your current job? <i>stf_job_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... az egészségi állapotával? / your health? <i>stf_health_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a személyes kapcsolataival? / your personal relationships? <i>stf_relation_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... azon idő mennyiségével, amelyet az Ön által kedvelt dolgokkal tölthetett? / the amount of time you could spend doing the things you like? <i>stf_timeuse_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakókörnyezete minőségével? / the quality of your living environment? <i>stf_livingenv_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a lakókörnyezetében sportolásra, pihenésre rendelkezésre álló helyekkel és zöldterületekkel? / recreational or green areas in your living area? <i>stf_greenarea_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
... a közszolgáltatások (egészségügy, oktatás, bürokrácia stb.) minőségével, megbízhatóságával, elérhetőségével? / quality, reliability, accessibility of public services (healthcare system, education system, bureaucracy etc.)? <i>stf_public_pre</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3.2 Érzelmi, hangulati állapot / Affective well-being

Az utóbbi négy hét során Ön milyen gyakran... / During the last 4 weeks how often...

1. soha / none of the time
 2. ritkán / a little of the time
 3. időnként / some of the time
 4. többnyire / most of the time
 5. mindig / all of the time
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

... volt nagyon ideges? / were you very nervous?	<i>being_nervous</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
--	----------------------	-----------------

... érezte magát annyira lehangoltnak, hogy semmi sem tudja felvidítani? / Feeling down in the dumps	<i>feel_down</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát nyugodtnak és békésnek? / Feeling calm and peaceful	<i>feel_calm</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát csüggedtnek és levertnek? / Feeling downhearted or depressed?	<i>feel_downhearted</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... volt boldog? were you happy?	<i>being_happy</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát magányosnak? / Feeling lonely?	<i>feel_lonely</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát stresszesnek? / Feeling stressed?	<i>feel_stressed</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99

Most gondoljon vissza az Ausztriába költözés előtti időszakra! Akkoriban milyen gyakran... / Now think back to the year before you moved to Austria! That time how often were you...

... volt nagyon ideges? / were you very nervous?	<i>being_nervous_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát annyira lehangoltnak, hogy semmi sem tudja felvidítani? / Feeling down in the dumps	<i>feel_down_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát nyugodtnak és békésnek? / Feeling calm and peaceful	<i>feel_calm_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát csüggedtnek és levertnek? / Feeling downhearted or depressed?	<i>feel_downhearted_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... volt boldog? were you happy?	<i>being_happy_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát magányosnak? / Feeling lonely?	<i>feel_lonely_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99
... érezte magát stresszesnek? / Feeling stressed?	<i>feel_stressed_pre</i>	1 2 3 4 5 98 99

3.3 Eudaimonikus jóllét / Eudaimonic well-being

Összességében mennyire érzi tartalmasnak azokat a dolgokat, amelyeket csinál? / Overall, how meaningful do you feel about the things you do? *meaningoflife*

0: Egyáltalán nem tartalmasak. / Not worthwhile at all.

10: Kifejezetten tartalmasak. / Completely worthwhile.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mennyire néz Ön reményvesztetten vagy bizakodóan a jövőbe? / How hopeless or optimistic are you about the future? *optimism*

0: Teljes mértékben reményvesztetten. / Completely without hope.

10: Teljes mértékben bizakodóan. / Completely hopeful.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mennyire igaz Önre az alábbi állítás: "Úgy érzem, szabadon eldönthetem, hogy hogyan éljem az életemet". / To what extent is it true in your case: „I feel free to choose how to live my life”

freelife

0: Egyáltalán nem igaz. / Not true at all.

10: Teljesen igaz. / Completely true.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Most gondoljon vissza az Ausztriába költözés előtti időszakra! / Now think back to the year before you moved to Austria!

Összességében mennyire érezte akkoriban tartalmasnak azokat a dolgokat, amelyeket csinált? / Overall, how meaningful did you feel about the things you do?

meaningoflife_pre

0: Egyáltalán nem tartalmasak. / Not worthwhile at all.

10: Kifejezetten tartalmasak. / Completely worthwhile.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mennyire nézett Ön akkoriban reményvesztetten vagy bizakodóan a jövőbe? / How hopeless or optimistic were you about the future?

optimism_pre

0: Teljes mértékben reményvesztetten. / Completely without hope.

10: Teljes mértékben bizakodóan. / Completely hopeful.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.

99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Akkoriban mennyire volt igaz Önre az alábbi állítás: "Úgy érzem, szabadon eldönthetem, hogy hogyan éljem az életemet". / To what extent was it true in your case: „I feel free to choose how to live my life”
freelife_pre

- 0: Egyáltalán nem igaz. / Not true at all.
 10: Teljesen igaz. / Completely true.
 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Bizalom / Trust

Elmondható-e Ön szerint, hogy a legtöbb emberben meg lehet bízni? / Would you say that most people can be trusted?
trust_others

- 0: Senkiben sem lehet bízni. / Do not trust any other.
 10: A legtöbb emberben meg lehet bízni. / Most people can be trusted.
 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Elmondható-e Ön szerint, hogy a lakókönyékén (Ausztriában) élő emberekben meg lehet bízni? / Would you say that people in your neighbourhood (in Austria) can be trusted?
trust_local

- 0: Senkiben sem lehet bízni. / Do not trust any other.
 10: A legtöbb emberben meg lehet bízni. / Most people can be trusted.
 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

Mennyire bízik meg Ön személy szerint a következő nemzeti intézményekben Ausztriában és Magyarországon? / Please tell me how much you personally trust each of the following national institutions in Austria and in Hungary?

- 0: Egyáltalán nem bízok benne. / I do not trust at all.
 10: Teljesen megbízok benne. / I completely trust.
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

	Ausztriában / In Austria	Magyarországon / In Hungary

... A politikai rendszerben? / In the political system?	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 <i>99 trust_politics_at</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 99 <i>trust_politics_hu</i>
... A jogrendszerben? / In the legal system?	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 <i>99 trust_legal_at</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 99 <i>trust_legal_hu</i>
... A kormányban? / In the government?	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 <i>99 trust_gov_at</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 99 <i>trust_gov_hu</i>
... A rendőrségben? / In the police?	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 <i>99 trust_police_at</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 99 <i>trust_police_hu</i>
... A médiában? / In the media?	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 <i>99 trust_media_at</i>	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 98 99 <i>trust_media_hu</i>

Záró kérdések: havi jövedelem / Final questions: monthly income

MIELŐTT AUSZTRIÁBA KÖLTÖZÖTT, havonta mennyi volt az ÖN NETTÓ JÖVEDELME összesen? Kérem vegyen figyelembe a fizetésen felül minden egyéb juttatást, támogatást és segítyt is (pl. gyés, családi pótlék, a vendéglátásban borralaló)! / BEFORE THE MOVE TO AUSTRIA, what was YOUR TOTAL NET INCOME per month? Please take into account any other benefits and allowances in addition to your salary (e.g. child support, family allowance, tipping in hospitality).

inc_p_1_pre_cat

- 0: Nem volt jövedelemem. / I did not have income.
1. 100 ezer Ft alatt / Below 100,000 HUF
 2. 101 – 200 ezer Ft / 100,000 – 200,000 HUF
 3. 201 – 300 ezer Ft / 201,000 – 300,000 HUF
 4. 301 – 400 ezer Ft / 301,000 – 400,000 HUF
 5. 401 – 500 ezer Ft / 401,000 – 500,000 HUF
 6. 501 – 750 ezer Ft / 501,000 – 750,000 HUF
 7. 751 – 1 millió Ft / 751,000 – 1,000,000 HUF
 8. 1 millió – 2 millió Ft / 1,000,000 – 2,000,000 HUF
 9. 2 millió – 4 millió Ft / 2,000,000 – 4,000,000 HUF
 10. 4 millió Ft felett / Above 4,000,000 HUF
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

MIELŐTT AUSZTRIÁBA KÖLTÖZÖTT, havonta mennyi volt az ÖN HÁZTARTÁSÁNAK HAVI NETTÓ JÖVEDELME összesen? Kérem vegyen figyelembe a fizetésen felül minden egyéb juttatást, támogatást és segítyt is (pl. gyés, családi pótlék, a

vendéglátásban borraivaló)! / BEFORE THE MOVE TO AUSTRIA, what was YOUR HOUSEHOLDS' TOTAL NET INCOME per month? Please take into account any other benefits and allowances in addition to your salary (e.g. child support, family allowance, tipping in hospitality).

inc_h_1_pre_cat

- 0: Nem volt jövedelmem. / I did not have income.
1. 100 ezer Ft alatt / Below 100,000 HUF
 2. 101 – 200 ezer Ft / 100,000 – 200,000 HUF
 3. 201 – 300 ezer Ft / 201,000 – 300,000 HUF
 4. 301 – 400 ezer Ft / 301,000 – 400,000 HUF
 5. 401 – 500 ezer Ft / 401,000 – 500,000 HUF
 6. 501 – 750 ezer Ft / 501,000 – 750,000 HUF
 7. 751 – 1 millió Ft / 751,000 – 1,000,000 HUF
 8. 1 millió – 2 millió Ft / 1,000,000 – 2,000,000 HUF
 9. 2 millió – 4 millió Ft / 2,000,000 – 4,000,000 HUF
 10. 4 millió Ft felett / Above 4,000,000 HUF
98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

JELENLEG havonta mennyi az ÖN NETTÓ JÖVEDELME összesen? Kérem vegyen figyelembe a fizetésen felül minden egyéb juttatást, támogatást és segélyt is (pl. Kinderbetreuungsgeld, Kinderabsetzbetrag, Familien Bonus Plus, a vendéglátásban borraivaló)! / CURRENTLY, what is YOUR TOTAL NET INCOME per month? Please take into account any other benefits and allowances in addition to your salary (e.g. Kinderbetreuungsgeld, Kinderabsetzbetrag, Familien Bonus Plus, tipping in hospitality).

inc_p_1_cat

- 0: Nincs jelenleg jövedelmem. / I do not have income now.
1. 250 € alatt / 250 € and below
 2. 251 - 500 €
 3. 501 - 750 €
 4. 751 - 1,000 €
 5. 1,001 - 1,300 €
 6. 1,301 - 1,600 €
 7. 1,601 - 1,900 €
 8. 1,901 - 2,200 €
 9. 2,201 - 2,500 €
 10. 2,501 - 3,000 €
 11. 3,001 - 3,500 €
 12. 3,501 - 4,000 €
 13. 4,001 - 5,000 €
 14. 5,001 - 6,000 €

15. 6,000 € felett / 6,001 € and above
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

JELENLEG havonta mennyi az ÖN HÁZTARTÁSÁNAK HAVI NETTÓ JÖVEDELME összesen? Kérem vegyen figyelembe a fizetésen felül minden egyéb juttatást, támogatást és segítyt is (pl. Kinderbetreuungsgeld, Kinderabsetzbetrag, Familien Bonus Plus, a vendéglátásban borraavaló)! / CURRENTLY, what is YOUR HOUSEHOLD'S TOTAL NET INCOME per month? Please take into account any other benefits and allowances in addition to your salary (e.g. Kinderbetreuungsgeld, Kinderabsetzbetrag, Familien Bonus Plus, tipping in hospitality).

inc_h_1_cat

- 0: Nincs jelenleg jövedelme a háztartásnak. / The household doesnot have income now.
1. 600 € alatt / 600 € and below
 2. 601 – 900 €
 3. 901 - 1,200 €
 4. 1,201 - 1,500 €
 5. 1,501 - 1,800 €
 6. 1,801 - 2,200 €
 7. 2,201 - 2,600 €
 8. 2,601 - 3,000 €
 9. 3,001 - 3,500 €
 10. 3,501 - 4,000 €
 11. 4,001 - 4,500 €
 12. 4,501 - 5,000 €
 13. 5,001 - 6,000 €
 14. 6,001 - 8,000 €
 15. 8,000 € felett / (8,001 € and above)
 98. Nem tudom. / I don't know.
 99. Nem kívánok válaszolni. / I don't want to answer.

LAST PAGE (FOR THE ONLINE VERSION)

A kutatócsoport nevében nagyon szépen köszönjük a felmérésben való részvételét! Amennyiben tudomása van olyan Ausztriában élő magyar ismerőséről, barátjáról, kollégájáról, aki Ön szerint kitöltené ezt a kérdőívet, kérjük, küldje el az elérhetőségét az alábbi email címre! Köszönjük!

A kutatásról, és annak eredményeiről több információt is megtalál az alábbi honlapon:
<https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/isr/research/rg-urban-transformation/migwell-well-being-and-migration-the-hungary-austria-migration-nexus>

Üdvözlettel,

A MIGWELL csapat
DDr. Josef Kohlbacher
Dr. Németh Ádám
Dr. Sümeghy Dávid

On behalf of the research team, thank you very much for your participation in the survey! If you know of a Hungarian friend or colleague living in Austria who would like to fill in this questionnaire, please send your contact details to the email address below. Thank you!

More information about the survey and its results can be found on the website below:
<https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/isr/research/rg-urban-transformation/migwell-well-being-and-migration-the-hungary-austria-migration-nexus>

Üdvözlettel,

A MIGWELL csapat
DDr. Josef Kohlbacher
Dr. Németh Ádám
Dr. Sümeghy Dávid